

D4.1: Report on the website

Author:

Carol Usher, MDR

Ariadne is funded by the European Commission's 7th Framework Programme.

Version 1.0 (*final*)

30th April 2013

Author:

Carol Usher

MDR Partners (Consulting) Ltd

Contributor:

Kate Fernie, MDR

Document History

- 19.04.2013 – Draft Version 0.1
- 23.04.2013 – Final version 1.0

ARIADNE is a project funded by the European Commission under the Community's Seventh Framework Programme, contract no. FP7-INFRASTRUCTURES-2012-1-313193. The views and opinions expressed in this presentation are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Website Content	4
2.1	Home Page	4
2.2	About.....	5
2.3	Events.....	6
2.4	Resources.....	7
2.5	News	7
2.6	Project Partners	8
2.7	Planned developments – Community section	9
2.8	Planned developments – Infrastructure portal.....	10
2.9	Partner Area.....	10
2.10	Email addresses.....	10
3.	Users, Registration & Roles	11
4.	Supported language content.....	11
5.	Web Statistics.....	12
5.1	Visits by Country	12
5.2	Traffic Sources.....	13
5.3	Referrals.....	13
6.	Conclusions	14
7.	References.....	14

1 Executive Summary

The Ariadne website was launched in month one of the project.

The project website will be the main access point for information about the project, its research and development programme and events, and for downloading its products in digital format. The website will provide access to the research infrastructure portal from month 18, from which researchers will be able to access datasets, tools and other resources.

MDR maintains and develops the project website with contributions from all partners. The website was introduced to the project partners at the kick-off meeting held in Rome on 7-8 February 2013.

The Ariadne website is built on a modern CMS platform allowing content to be managed effectively and efficiently by project managers and partners.

The frontend makes use of responsive design techniques to enable use of the site across multiple devices and platforms including smartphones and tablets.

Content is consistently marked up with valid and semantic HTML to help increase search engine presence and to ensure content is accessible to screen readers and through other accessibility tools.

News and event content is supplemented with Schema.org metadata to improve search results and machine readability.

There are two registered domain names for Ariadne:

- ariadne-infrastructure.eu
- ariadne-proiect.eu

ariadne-infrastructure.eu is the main domain name, the alternative name (Ariadne-project.eu) redirects to this main domain name.

The website will be linked to the research infrastructure portal, which is being developed by CNR and will be maintained by UoY-ADS, from month 18.

2. Website Content

2.1 Home Page

The Adriane home page presents an overview of the project with distinctive images from partners, a brief easily readable overview of the project goals and dynamic content showing latest news, events and social network activity from Twitter.

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

ARIADNE English Register Login

About Events Resources News Partners

Ariadne

About Ariadne Read More

ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology. There is now a large availability of archaeological digital datasets that all together span different periods, domains and regions; more are continuously created as a result of the increasing use of IT. They are the accumulated outcome of the research of individuals, teams and institutions, but form a vast and fragmented corpus and their potential has been constrained by difficult access and non-homogenous perspectives.

Latest News See All

- Apr 17 2013 Press release
- Feb 15 2013 Call for papers EAA2013
- Feb 14 2013 Open Humanities Awards

Events See All

- Nov 19 2013 MTSR 2013
- Nov 11 2013 CHNT 2013
- Sep 22 2013 TPD 2013

Twitter Follow Us

Registration is open for AIAC 2013, the international congress of classical archaeology: <http://t.co/uXRzsbY2xg>
35 minutes ago

RT AWMC_UNC By using connections in Pleiades, one can establish network relationships between 'places', as demonstrated by...
<http://t.co/3AA6lsbT0J>
12 hours ago
Retweeted by Ariadne_Network and 3 others

Call for participation in Digital Heritage 2013 is now open: <http://t.co/CNJTiv1p3U>
16 hours ago

Call for papers for IEEE BigData 2013 - big data in the arts, humanities and culture
<http://t.co/q3tOhUDvJ4>

Copyright © 2012 Ariadne. All rights reserved.
Ariadne is funded by the European Commission's [7th Framework Programme](#).
[Contact us](#) | [Legal](#) | [Press](#)

SEVENTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

2.2 About

About

[Events](#)[Resources](#)[News](#)[Partners](#)

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/About>

This section of the website provides an overview of the project and includes sub menus for a detailed introduction to Digital Infrastructures for Archaeological Research and information on proposed project activities:

- Community building and dissemination
- Transnational access
- Joint research activities - developing advanced integrated services

ARIADNE

English | Register | Login

About | Events | Resources | News | Partners

Ariadne > About

About Ariadne

ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology. There is now a large availability of archaeological digital datasets that all together span different periods, domains and regions; more are continuously created as a result of the increasing use of IT. They are the accumulated outcome of the research of individuals, teams and institutions, but form a vast and fragmented corpus and their potential has been constrained by difficult access and non-homogenous perspectives.

Ariadne will enable trans-national access of researchers to data centres, tools and guidance, and the creation of new Web-based services based on common interfaces to data repositories, availability of reference datasets and usage of innovative technologies. It will stimulate new research avenues in the field of archaeology, relying on the comparison, re-use and integration into current research of the outcomes of past and on-going field and laboratory activity. Such data are scattered amongst diverse collections, datasets, unpublished fieldwork reports (grey literature), and in publications. The latter still being the main source of knowledge sharing. Ariadne will contribute to the creation of a new community of researchers ready to exploit the contribution of Information Technology and to incorporate it in the body of established archaeological research methodology.

To achieve this result the project will use a number of integrating technologies that build on common features of the currently available datasets, and on integrating actions that will build a vibrant community of use.

Activities
Introduction

Share | Facebook | LinkedIn | RSS | Twitter

2.3 Events

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Events>

Partners are able to recommend events for inclusion on the site through a shared, controlled document, which is subject to a scheduled review. A content administrator then adds new events to the site.

All event content provides a brief overview of the event along with dates and venue. A direct link to the event website is also included.

ARIADNE English Register Login

About Events Resources News Partners

Ariadne > Events

Events Share | Facebook | Twitter

Upcoming Events

MAY 13 2013 [Congreso AIAC 2013](#)
Mon 13 May 00:00 - Fri 17 May 00:00
Conference
Venue: Mérida, Spain

AIAC The 18th International Congress of Classical Archaeology will be held in Mérida in May 2013. On this occasion the slogan will be "Centre and periphery in the ancient world" it will be jointly organised by the National Museum of Roman Art, the Government of Extremadura Department of Education and Culture and the Catalan Institute of Classical Archaeology.

JUN 13 2013 [MAPPA: Opening the Past](#)
Thu 13 Jun 00:00 - Sat 15 Jun 00:00
Venue: Pisa, Italy

Opening the Past Archaeology of the Future
Opening the Past 2013 is the final conference of the MAPPA project: it aims to present the results of the project and to discuss interesting and new proposals during the sessions:

- Predictivity in archaeology
- Open Data in Archaeology
- Open Access in Archaeology
- Urban geoarchaeology

JUL 22 2013 [JCDL 2013](#)
Mon 22 Jul 00:00 - Fri 26 Jul 00:00
Digital Libraries at the Crossroads
Venue: Indianapolis, Indiana, USA

JCDL The ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL 2013) is a major international forum focusing on digital libraries and associated technical, practical, organizational, and social issues. JCDL encompasses the many meanings of the term digital libraries, including (but not limited to) new forms of information institutions and organizations; operational information systems with all manner of digital content; new means of selecting, collecting, organizing, distributing, and accessing digital content; theoretical models of information media, including document genres and electronic publishing; and theory and practice of use of managed content in science and education.

2.4 Resources

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Resources>

The resources section of the website includes publications, press and links. Any presentations given about the project by the project partners will also be available for viewing online and for downloading.

In due course, a link to a Standards Registry will also be included along with links to other useful resources as considered appropriate.

2.5 News

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News>

The news section offers a frequently updated insight to project events and activities, and will be supplemented by content from scheduled newsletters.

2.6 Project Partners

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/News>

The Partners page presents an overview of all project partners, along with their logos. Full details about the partner and a link to their website is available on individual partner pages.

Partners are encouraged to contribute content to their own pages where appropriate.

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE website's 'Partners' page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Partners' selected. Below the navigation bar, the page title 'Partners' is displayed. The main content area features a grid of partner logos and names, organized by country. On the right side, there is a vertical list of partner names. At the bottom right, there is a social media sharing button.

Country	Partner Name	Role
Italy	PIN Sclari - Polo Universitario 'Città di Prato'	Coordinator
UK	ods Archaeology Data Service	Deputy Coordinator
Netherlands	DANS Data Archiving and Networked Services	
Germany	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	
UK	MDR Partners	
Greece	Athena Research Centre	
Italy	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	
Austria	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft m.b.H.	
Ireland	The Discovery Programme LBG	
Sweden	Swedish National Data Service	
Spain	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Instituto de Ciencias del Patrimonio	
Slovenia	Znanstvenoraziskovalni Center Slovenske Akademije Znanosti in Umetnosti	
UK	University of Glamorgan	
Hungary	NOK Hungarian National Museum/National Heritage Protection Centre	
Cyprus	Slovenia The Cyprus Institute Limited	
Greece	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas	
Czech Republic	Institute of Archaeology AS CR	
Austria	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften	
Italy	AIAC	
Bulgaria	National Institute of Archaeology and Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	
Italy	Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico delle biblioteche italiane e per le informazioni bibliografiche	
Romania	Asociația Arheo Vest	
France	Inrap Institut national de recherches archéologiques préventives	
Netherlands	Universiteit Leiden	

- PIN - Coordinator
- ADS - Deputy Coordinator
- KNAW-DANS
- DAI
- MDR
- Athena-RC
- CNR
- SRFG
- Discovery
- SND
- CSIC
- ZRC-SAZU
- UoG
- MNM NOK
- CYI-STARC
- FORTH-ICS
- ARUP-CAS
- ÖAW
- AIAC
- NIAM-BAS
- MIBAC-ICCU
- ARHEO
- INRAP
- LU

2.7 Planned developments – Community section

The project is working on developing a ‘Community’ section of the website to include information on the registration process, and links to social networking sites.

Social Networking

Twitter : Ariadne Network

https://twitter.com/Ariadne_Network

A Twitter account has been newly established and tweeting is underway. Tweets are displayed on the homepage.

LinkedIn

A group has been established for ARIADNE at:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=4966050&trk=anet_ug_hm

Slideshare

A Slideshare account has been established for the project: [ariadnenetwork](#). This channel will be used to share project presentations, reports and other publications.

Slideshare will be used to embed documents on the Ariadne website to enable visitors to browse the full document without the need to download them. Presentations and documents can also be viewed directly from slideshare.

A **YouTube** channel will be established for the project. The intention is to use this channel to publish videos about the project, the research infrastructure and its activities.

Other media channels

Flickr

Mendeley

Academia.edu

Zotero

iamResearcher

zotero

2.8 Planned developments – Infrastructure portal

The Ariadne website will be linked to an infrastructure portal which will be designed and implemented within the framework of work packages 12 and 13. The portal will provide access to the content and also to a metadata registry and other tools and resources.

2.9 Partner Area

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/Partner-Area>
Restricted to project partners

The partner area provides a section of the site dedicated to storing and sharing project materials, documents and deliverables amongst project partners. Only project partners are given access on login and menu items, and content remains invisible to the public.

Grant agreement
Kick-off meeting
Communication tools
Reporting templates
Community

2.10 Email addresses

A number of accompanying email addresses have been created that redirect to the appropriate members of the Management team.

- info@ariadne-infrastructure.eu
- network@ariadne-infrastructure.eu
- press@ariadne-infrastructure.eu
- event@ariadne-infrastructure.eu

3. Users, Registration & Roles

The website supports multiple user roles and permissions, allowing project managers to grant subsets of users the right to see and modify areas of the site otherwise restricted to normal users. These are:

- **General users:** can see the public pages of the site.
- **Registered users:** will receive email newsletters etc.
- **Project users:** can log in, view and edit reserved project pages (members area) and the partner pages.
- **News editors:** can log in, view and edit reserved project pages (members area), the partner pages and news pages.
- **Admin users:** can log in, add containers and content etc.

4. Supported language content

Static content of the website will be provided in several languages;

- The main languages to be supported: English, Italian, French, German
- The additional partner languages which may also be included are: Greek, Swedish, Slovenian, Hungarian, Czech, Bulgarian, Romanian and Dutch

5. Web Statistics

The Ariadne project website uses Google Analytics to track and analyse traffic to the website.

Visits to the website since the launch of the website were reported from 36 countries.

The number of visits from 9 February to 18 April 2013 was: 935 of which 474 were unique visits.

4,892 pages have been viewed since the start of the project with 3,343 being unique visits.

5.1 Visits by Country

Ariadne – Visits by Country

9/02/2013 – 18/04/2013

Source: Google Analytics

Note: While there are systems in place to prevent visits from site administrators (by IP and by website account), these systems are not 100% reliable and may result in inflated visit counts from the UK.

Google Analytics does not record visits from users with JavaScript disabled. There are no accurate figures for the percentage of users with JavaScript disabled, but it is generally considered to be somewhere between 2% to 3%.

Source: Google Analytics

5.2 Traffic Sources

The diagram below indicates the percentage of traffic to the website by source.

5.3 Referrals

The total number of visits via referrals since the beginning of the project was 5,283 from 433 referrals. For this reporting period there have been 1,804 visits from 194 referrals. The chart below identifies the top 20 referrals for last 6 months.

6. Conclusions

The project website was successfully launched during the first month of the project. The initial web statistics show that the website is already providing a point of access to information about the project from users in Europe and internationally. Plans are in place to develop the content of the website itself and to develop a presence for the project on social networking channels, and work is underway to design, specify and develop the research infrastructure portal to provide researchers with access to Ariadne datasets.

Over the next year the website will continue to develop both in terms of its content and its user base. Progress will be reported at month 18 in D4.3 the first periodic dissemination report.

7. References

Ariadne Description of Work

D4.2 Ariadne Initial dissemination plan